

Test for validity of Eyring's hypothesis of co-ordination number of some metals

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Abstract : A method for the calculation of atom to hole ratio and hence co-ordination number of metals has been proposed which tests the validity of Eyring's hypothesis. Our method is based on the comparison of Trouton's rule with Richard's rule which will correspond to atom to hole ratio because one atom is replaced by a hole on melting and each atom loses all co-ordinated nearest neighbours on evaporation. After calculating the atom to hole ratio, co-ordination number has been found out.

In the present study, twenty metals of different structures have been selected to test the validity of Eyring's hypothesis. It has been observed that the Eyring's hypothesis coincides approximately in majority of cases and deviates in some cases. It has been suggested that the discrepancy may be either due to some special arrangement of atoms in metals or due to deviation from Trouton's and Richard's rule.

Keywords : Atom to hole ratio, co-ordination number, Trouton's and Richard's rule.

Introduction

While explaining the heat of fusion¹ by hole theory, Eyring² made assumption that the average co-ordination number of metals is twelve and twelve nearest neighbours of each atom in a close-packed solid is replaced by a hole on melting. Also that one twelfth of the total chemical bonds are broken and the atom to hole ratio will be 11 : 1. This has, to the best of our knowledge, not been tested theoretically or experimentally.

In the present communication, we have proposed a method for the calculation of atom to hole ratio and hence the co-ordination number of metals having different crystal structures.

Methodology :

Our method of calculation of co-ordination number of metals is based on the comparison of Trouton's rule³ ($H_v/T_v = S_v \equiv$ entropy of vaporization) with Richard's rule⁴ ($H_f/T_f = S_f \equiv$ entropy of fusion = 2 cal/K), where H_v and H_f , T_b and T_f are heats of vaporization and fusion, boiling point and fusion temperature respectively. On melting one atom is replaced by a hole and each atom loses all co-ordinated nearest neighbours (i.e. eleven on

the average) on evaporation. With the atom to hole ratio, the co-ordination number of metals are found.

For this purpose, the data on heats of vaporization and fusion, boiling point and fusion temperature are collected for twenty metals under consideration of different crystal structures from Perry and Chilton⁵ and Lange's⁶ handbooks which have been listed in Table 1. Further, we calculated S_v and S_f on dividing heats of vaporization and fusion by boiling and fusion temperature respectively. Finally, the ratio S_v to S_f is calculated to get the atom to hole ratio for every metal. With the help of atom to hole ratio, the co-ordination number of metals is found out and entered in Table 1.

Results and discussion

From the calculation of co-ordination number, it is revealed that the Eyring's assumption of 12 co-ordination number of metals coincides in majority of cases and the values cluster around 11 in some cases. In case of Li, Cd, B and Fe, Eyring's assumption is ruled out. The large deviation in CN in case of above metals may be due to some special arrangement of atoms in the metals concerned. The values of CN which cluster around 11 may

Table 1

Metals	Fusion temp. T_f	H_f (Cals/mol)	$H_f/T_f = S_f$ (Cals/K/mol)	B.P. Tb	H_v (Cals/mol)	$H_v/T_b = S_v$ (Cals/K/mol)	$S_v/S_f = A/H$ ratio	CN approx.	Crystal type
Li	452	1100	2.433	1645	32250	19.605	8.06	9	bcc
Na	307.7	630	1.699	1187	23120	19.470	11.46	12	bcc
K	336.5	574	1.705	1049	18920	18.036	10.58	12	bcc
Rb	312.1	525	1.682	952	18110	19.020	11.31	12	bcc
Cs	301.4	500	1.659	963	16320	16.947	10.21	11	bcc
Ba	977	1400	1.433	1911	35670	18.665	13.02	14	bcc
Mo	2895	6660	2.300	5073	128000	25.230	10.97	12	bcc
Fe	1803	3560	1.974	3008	84600	28.125	14.25	15	bcc
Al	933	2550	2.733	2330	61020	26.188	9.58	11	bcc
Ca	1124	2230	1.984	1760	36580	20.784	10.47	12	fcc
Cu	1356	3110	2.293	2868	72810	25.387	11.07	12	fcc
Sr	1030	2190	2.126	1657	33610	20.280	9.54	10	fcc
Ag	1233.5	2700	2.188	2485	60720	24.430	11.16	12	fcc
Au	1336	3030	2.268	3239	81800	25.254	11.13	12	fcc
Pt	2046.5	4700	2.296	4673	107000	22.897	9.97	11	fcc
Pb	600.4	1224	2.038	2017	42060	20.853	10.23	11	fcc
Mg	923	2160	2.340	1380	32520	23.565	10.07	11	hcp
Ni	1728	4200	2.430	3003	87300	29.071	11.96	13	hcp
Zn	692.5	1595	2.303	1180	27430	23.240	10.09	11	hcp
Cd	593.9	1460	2.458	1038	23870	22.996	9.35	10	hcp

be assumed to follow the Eyring's hypothesis because it is very close to 12. The discrepancy may be supposed to be due to deviation from Trouton's and Richard's rule.

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